

HISPANIC REVIEW

UNIVERSITY of PENNSYLVANIA

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February 15, 1995

Professor María Dolores Dobón
Mary Baldwin College
Staunton, VA 24401-9983

Dear Professor Dobón:

We have received a review copy of the following book:

Azorín. Tomás Rueda. Ed., intro., y notas de Miguel Ángel Lozano Marco.
Literatura y crítica 14. Alicante: Instituto de cultura Juan Gil-Albert, 1994. 212
pages.

We have fixed a 750 word limit for the review of this book, and we
would appreciate it very much if you would consent to do the review for us.

Reviewers are asked to submit their review manuscripts no later than six months
after the date on which they receive their review copies. Upon completion of your
review, the book would of course become your property.

If, as we hope, you accept our invitation, we shall send you complete instructions
for the preparation of your review, together with the review copy.

Sincerely yours,

Ignacio Javier López